

Operational Storage: Think short and long term

Store & Manage

Secure Active Data

Every stage of the data lifecycle centers around data storage. Proper storage maintenance throughout the lifecycle is imperative to ensure data remains secure and adheres to recommended safety protocols.

- **Data Safety:** Protect the welfare of research participants and confirm the integrity of research data. Harvard's [Data Safety system](#) supports the submission, review, and management of data use.
- **Data Security:** Ensure confidential and sensitive data is maintained. Harvard maintains five Data Security Levels. Review the [Research Data Security Levels with Examples](#) to determine your risk level.
- **Software:** Protect your software systems using strategies like anti-virus software, updating applications and OS, firewall, and anti-intrusion software. Digital access should be limited to those that need it.
- **Hardware:** Ensure appropriate security controls for the physical location(s) where your computers, servers, and data storage reside. Physical access should be restricted to those that need access.

Determine Appropriate Data Storage Locations

Review institutional storage options to better understand where to store data based on behavior, performance, and means of access. The type of data you are working with, or the Data Security Level, will dictate where and how that data needs to be stored or handled.

- **Harvard University Collaborative Matrix:** Aligns Harvard's Data Security Levels with storage platforms
- **HMS IT Research Data Storage Offerings:** HMS offers three primary storage types with distinct behaviors, performance, and means of access
- **FAS Data Storage Offerings:** FASRC offers three different software applications with variety of performance characteristics

Create a Data Backup Plan

Having at least one backup can help prevent data mishaps. Harvard systems automatically provide secure backup in geographically distributed locations.

- **CrashPlan (Code42):** Ensures critical data is recoverable in the event of a loss or compromise or data. [CrashPlan is available to HMS and HSDM](#) quad-based personnel for free. [CrashPlan is also available for FAS departments, Central Administration, and other schools](#) through Harvard University IT (HUIT).
 - Backs up continually over almost any network on or off-campus

Harvard Research Data Management Lifecycle Checklist

- Recovers documents from any computer via a web browser
- Stores document copies for a minimum of 60 days

Research data that is temporarily not in Harvard systems benefits from following the 3-2-1 Rule.

- **3-2-1 Rule:** General fail-proof backup strategy:
 - Three copies of the data (e.g., original + external/local + external/remote)
 - Two types of storage formats (e.g., external hard drive + cloud location)
 - One storage type is offsite (e.g. geographically distributed location)

Resolve Access Permissions

Ensure data is always shared with the PI and always resides in a shared location with more than one owner to help support the longevity and sustainability of research. Individual data should be moved to a shared location prior to completion of a project or departure from a lab. Access permissions also apply to a variety of storage locations including Electronic Lab Notebooks and website content.

★ **Utilize the [RDM Offboarding Checklist](#) to offboard employees or team members from the lab or project**
When employees leave, they take their skills and institutional knowledge with them. It is important to record essential informative information related to projects and datasets to ensure the success of future users. Use the [RDM Offboarding Checklist](#) and [Knowledge Transfer File Template](#) to guide the knowledge transfer process.

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Evaluate & Archive

Assess Data Retention

Determine what data must be retained or destroyed for contractual, legal, or regulatory purposes, and how long the data will be retained and preserved. Additionally, data and related records might be identified for permanent storage as a part of the historical record of a discipline or institution, or as intellectual property.

- **Harvard Research Records Retention**: Researchers have certain obligations to record, maintain and retain research records, and to make those records available for grant monitoring and auditing purposes. In general, essential research records should be retained for a period of no fewer than seven (7) years after the end of a research project or activity.
- **Essential Research Records**:
 - substantiating grant applications or demonstrating compliance with contractual terms
 - substantiating published research and patents, whether the research is sponsored or not
 - substantiating research described in grant proposals and other funding requests
 - records considered for permanent preservation and access by the Archives and Records Management Program at the Center for the History of Medicine

Appraise Data for Archiving

A small percentage of data and related records may be identified for permanent storage as a part of the historical record of a discipline, institution, or as intellectual property. Harvard takes on all costs and security for archived data and records after appraisal and acquisition.

- **Records eligible for permanent retention maybe those that:**
 - document a breakthrough
 - are generated by a lab or individual who had a great impact on the field
 - are highly reusable in a particular area of research

★ **Understand the difference between “archiving” and “long-term storage”**

Permanent retention or archiving is the ongoing migration of electronic formats and storage costs, as well as care, maintenance, and access services for the records in perpetuity. Long-term storage and preservation seek to ensure data will be available in a persistent and accessible format for the specific period outlined by your funder and institution.

Appropriately Dispose Data

Once the research has concluded, determine which data and records are safe to dispose of, including how you will permanently remove sensitive data or project data.

- [Retention & Maintenance of Research Records & Data Frequently Asked Questions \(FAQ\)](#): Guides the retention and maintenance of research records by Harvard faculty and staff.
- [General Records Schedule \(GRS\) and Research Records](#): Details how long to retain different types of records and whether to send records to an archive or destroy them when they are no longer required.
- [In-Office Destruction Documentation Form](#): Used to document in-office destruction of records whose retention period has expired.

★ **Consult the Center for the History of Medicine [Archives and Records Management Program](#)**

The ARM program can assist you with appraising your research for long-term historical value, and help managing and disposing of data or records associated with your research.